

The Senegalese Administration: Crisis, Structural Change, and Adaptive Strategies

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Abstract: Since independence in 1960, the Senegalese administration has evolved in a constant tension between the need to preserve institutional continuity and the imperative to adapt to socio-economic, political and technological change. This article analyzes the major phases of administrative reform, from the socialist period (1960-2000) to the Abdoulaye Wade regime (2000-2012), up to the modernization policies driven by the Plan Sénégal Émergent (PSE) and Projet Sénégal 2050. Drawing on Loneux and Bouillon's *Approches Communicationnelles des Organisations* (ACO), the sociology of norms, and Abdoulaye-Bara Diop's sociological anchors, the study highlights a dual movement: structural evolution (laws, organization charts, technologies) and normative adaptation (changes in practices and routines).

Case studies of public companies in crisis (SNR, La Poste, Dakar Dem Dikk, SOGEP, SONACOS) and key ministries (Finance, Fonction Publique) illustrate the challenges of governance, communication and coordination. An in-depth chapter explores organizational dynamics, organizational change and improving service to the public, drawing on authors such as Eric Giuily (strategic communication) and Edgar Schein (organizational culture). Comparative analysis of periods and organizational dynamics highlights the importance of integrating communication, norm governance and the interplay of actors for sustainable reforms.

Keywords: *public administration, Senegal, administrative reform, , adaptation, public enterprises, ministries, organizational change, public service., organizational communication, norms, adaptation, public enterprises, ministries, organizational change, public service.*

1. Introduction

Senegal's public administration, heir to a French colonial bureaucratic model, has been faced since 1960 with the need to reconcile institutional stability with adaptation to global and local dynamics. This challenge is crucial in a context marked by globalization, digital transition, and a growing demand for transparency and efficiency. The Projet Sénégal 2050 emphasizes that "the quality and efficiency of public action are key to the Nation's competitiveness and resilience" (République du Sénégal, 2023). This ambition places the administration, its public companies (such as SENELEC or La Poste) and its ministries (Finance, Civil Service) at the heart of development strategies. The central issue is: how does the Senegalese administration, through its public companies and ministries, articulate structural evolution (new laws, organization charts, digital tools) with normative adaptation (transformation of practices, routines and mentalities) to

improve service to the public? This tension is exacerbated by the financial crises of public enterprises (SNR, La Poste) and the challenges of inter-ministerial coordination. This article combines a multidisciplinary theoretical framework, case studies and a detailed chapter on organizational dynamics, organizational change and public service to analyze these issues.

2. Theoretical framework

2.1 *Approches Communicationnelles des Organisations (ACO)* Catherine Loneux and Jean-Luc Bouillon (2012) define public organizations as entities "constituted by and in communication" (Loneux & Bouillon, 2012). Communication is a constitutive process of practices, professional identities and power relations. In Senegal, reforms such as dematerialization require internal and external communication to overcome resistance.

2.2 Sociology of norms and adaptation

analyzes the explicit (laws) and implicit (routines) norms that structure public policies. Normative adaptation requires collective appropriation, integrating contextual constraints (digital divide, cultural inertia).

2.3 *Sociological anchors* (Abdoulaye-Bara Diop) Abdoulaye-Bara Diop (1981) shows that Senegalese social structures, particularly Wolof, influence authority relationships and legitimacy in administration, creating a hybridity between traditional and bureaucratic norms.

2.4 *A critical look at the transfer of models* (Christian Le Moënne) Christian Le Moënne (2008) criticizes the non-contextualized import of models such as New Public Management, arguing for hybridization with local realities.

2.5 *Organizational dynamics and the interplay of actors* (Boniface Bampoky, Robert Simons, Eric Giuily, Edgar Schein) Boniface Bampoky (2012, 2013) highlights procedural management control in Senegalese public enterprises, limiting innovation (Bampoky & Meyssonnier, 2012). Robert Simons (1995) distinguishes diagnostic control (focused on financial results) from interactive control (favoring innovation). Eric Giuily (1992) emphasizes communication as a "decision parameter" (Giuily, 1992). Edgar Schein (2010) analyzes organizational culture as a brake or lever on change, particularly relevant to understanding resistance in Senegalese administration.

3. The Senegalese administration is based on a centralized model, with ministries in Dakar and decentralized services. Public enterprises (SENELEC, SONACOS) and ministries (Finance, Civil Service) are the pillars of public action, but suffer from bureaucratic red tape and poor interoperability of information systems.

4. Major reform phases
4.1 *The socialist period (1960-2000)* Under Senghor and Diouf, the administration favored stability, with centralized planning. Public enterprises, such as SONACOS, were supported by subsidies, but their management was inefficient. Ministries, such as the Ministry of Finance, exercised rigid tutelage, limiting autonomy.

4.2 *The regime of Me Abdoulaye Wade (2000-2012)* Wade introduced liberal reforms, with the creation of agencies and infrastructure projects. However, organizational instability and a lack of internal communication hampered progress, particularly in state-owned enterprises.

4.3 *The era of the Plan Sénégal Émergent (2014-2024)* The PSE emphasizes dematerialization (Sen-État Services), results-based management and simplification of procedures. Challenges include the digital divide (46% Internet access by 2023, ITU) and cultural inertia.

4.4 Prospects for Projet Sénégal 2050; Projet Sénégal 2050 aims for an "agile and inclusive" state, with a connected administration. Public enterprises and ministries are called upon to adopt technologies such as AI, but organizational resistance persists.

5. Case studies: problematic public companies and ministries

5.1 Société Nationale de Recouvrement (SNR)

SNR has equity of -86.7 billion FCFA (Libération, 2025).

Bampoky (2013) criticizes procedural control, while Simons (1995) suggests interactive control. The Ministry of Finance fails to coordinate restructuring, and internal communication is weak.

5.2 SN La Poste La Poste has equity of -143 billion FCFA (DPBEP, 2025). Loneux and Bouillon (2012) point to a lack of organizational communication, while the standards study notes a lack of normative ownership. The Ministry of the Digital Economy and the Ministry of Finance are struggling to coordinate their efforts.

5.3 Dakar Dem Dikk Dakar Dem Dikk has -60.7 billion FCFA in equity (DPBEP, 2025). Schein (2010) explains resistance by a rigid organizational culture. The Ministry of Transport lacks coordination with the Ministry of Finance. 5.4 SOGEPASOGEPA has equity of -28.5 billion FCFA (Libération, 2025). Our approach highlights the absence of normative appropriation. The Ministry of Urban Planning and the Ministry of Finance suffer from fragmented communication.

5.5 SONACOS SONACOS has shareholders' equity of 10.068 billion FCFA for a share capital of 20.234 billion (DPBEP, 2025). Bampoky (2012) criticizes the absence of a long-term strategy. Ministry of Agriculture and Ministry of Finance lack coordination

5.6 Ministry of Finance. The Ministry of Finance favors diagnostic control (Simons, 1995), limiting innovation. Giuily (1992) recommends strategic communication to improve coordination with public enterprises.

5.7 Ministry of the Civil Service. The Ministère de la Fonction Publique is struggling to modernize practices, held back by a rigid organizational culture (Schein, 2010). Loneux and Bouillon (2012) insist on constitutive communication to accompany change.

6. Organizational dynamics, organizational change and service to the public

6.1 Organizational dynamics: tensions between control and innovation. Organizational dynamics in Senegalese administration are marked by a tension between bureaucratic control and the need for innovation. Boniface Bampoky (2012, 2013) shows that public enterprises, such as SNR or La Poste, adopt a procedural management control, focused on compliance with budgets and procedures, to the detriment of a strategic vision. Robert Simons (1995) distinguishes between diagnostic control, which is dominant in Senegal, and interactive control, which promotes organizational learning. For example, the Dakar Dem Dikk crisis illustrates rigid diagnostic control, with a poorly maintained fleet and union conflicts, and no innovation mechanisms to meet user needs. Ministries, such as the Ministry of Finance, reproduce this logic, with supervision focused on financial compliance. Edgar Schein (2010) explains that organizational culture, defined as a set of shared beliefs and practices, hinders change when employees perceive reforms as a threat to their professional identity. In the case of La Poste, employee resistance to dematerialization reflects a culture rooted in traditional practices, such as manual mail processing.

6.2 Organizational change: resistance and levers

Organizational change, essential to modernizing the administration, comes up against several obstacles. Sahite Gaye (2017) points out that normative adaptation requires collective appropriation of the new rules. For example, the Sen-État Services platform aims to simplify administrative procedures, but its adoption is hampered by insufficient training for agents and a digital divide (46% Internet access by 2023, ITU). Edgar Schein (2010) identifies three stages in managing change: unfreezing (recognition of the need for change), transition (adoption of new practices), and refreezing (stabilization of practices). In Senegal, thawing is often initiated by structural reforms (such as the PSE), but transition is hampered by cultural and organizational resistance. Eric Giuily (1992) insists on communication as a strategic lever: "Communication is not simply a matter of accompanying the decision, it must be a parameter of the decision" (Giuily, 1992). In state-owned companies such as SOGÉPA, the absence of clear internal communication on restructuring objectives fuels conflicts between management and employees. Ministries, such as the Ministry of the Civil Service, need to invest in participative training to facilitate the appropriation of reforms. The interplay of actors, analyzed by Simons (1995), plays a key role. In Dakar Dem Dikk, tensions between unions, management and ministerial authorities (Transport, Finance) are blocking reforms. A participatory approach, involving agents in the co-construction of new practices, could reduce this resistance, as suggested by Gaye (2017).

6.3 Public service: towards a user-centric administration

Improving public service is a central objective of the PSE and *Projet Sénégal 2050*, which aim for a "user-centric" administration. However, public enterprises in crisis, such as La Poste and Dakar Dem Dikk, are struggling to meet citizens' expectations. For example, delays in postal deliveries or the frequent breakdowns of Dakar Dem Dikk buses degrade service quality. Loneux and Bouillon (2012) point out that external communication, essential for building citizen confidence, is often neglected. Campaigns such as those of the Government Information Office (BIG) post-2024 show an effort to improve digital communication, but they remain limited to major cities.

Abdoulaye-Bara Diop (1981) points out that citizens' expectations are influenced by socio-cultural dynamics, such as the need for proximity and personalization in interactions with the administration. For example, in rural areas, users prefer physical counters to digital platforms, underlining the importance of a hybrid approach. Christian Le Moëne (2008) criticizes the import of e-governance models that are disconnected from local realities, such as the digital divide or regional disparities.

Initiatives such as the digital one-stop shops in Thiès and Saint-Louis, supported by the Senegal 2050 Project, illustrate a desire to bring administration closer to citizens. However, their success depends on three levers: the training of agents (Schein, 2010), effective external communication (Giuily, 1992), and the integration of socio-cultural dynamics (Diop, 1981). For example, involving community leaders in the promotion of digital services could bridge the digital divide and boost user confidence.

6.4 Applied case studies

SNR: Lack of transparency in receivables management undermines user confidence. Clear external communication, such as public performance reports, could restore legitimacy, in line with Giuily's (1992) recommendations.

La Poste: Competition from digital services is depriving La Poste of its traditional customer base. A strategy of organizational change, combining training and communication (Schein, 2010), is needed to reposition the company as a digital player.

Dakar Dem Dikk: Frequent breakdowns undermine public service. Interactive control (Simons, 1995) and participative communication with users could improve transport quality.

Ministry of Finance: Insufficient inter-ministerial coordination hinders reforms. Strategic communication (Giully, 1992) between ministries and public enterprises is essential.

Ministry of the Civil Service: Training of civil servants remains inadequate. A freeze-transition-freeze approach (Schein, 2010) could facilitate the adoption of new practices.

7. Evolution vs. adaptation: cross-sectional analysis

The analysis of periods (1960-2000, 2000-2012, 2014-present) and case studies shows a gap between structural evolution and normative adaptation. Public companies and ministries illustrate this gap: structural reforms (dematerialization, recapitalization) are rapid, but normative adaptation (changes in practices) is hampered by cultural resistance (Schein, 2010), a lack of communication (Loneux & Bouillon, 2012), and actor conflicts (Simons, 1995).

8. Discussion: paradoxes and levers - a closer look at the field of organizational communication

Our findings show that the challenges of administrative reform in Senegal cannot be viewed solely from an economic or public management perspective. They must also be analyzed as complex communicational processes, in the sense of *Approches Communicationnelles des Organisations (ACO)*, where communication is not limited to an accompanying tool but constitutes the very backbone of organizational construction (Loneux & Bouillon, 2012; Taylor & Van Every, 2014).

8.1 The stability/flexibility paradox: a communication challenge

The stability/flexibility paradox, often described in public management literature (Denhardt & Denhardt, 2015), takes on a singular dimension in Senegalese administration. Public organizations, in particular public enterprises such as La Poste and SNR, are invested with a symbolic mission of state continuity and universal service. This continuity is embodied in practices, rituals and an inherited organizational culture (Schein, 2010) that values permanence and predictability.

However, today's environment, marked by the digital transition, the globalization of governance standards and rising citizen expectations, demands strategic and organizational flexibility. In the context of ACOs, this tension can be read as a conflict between two communication regimes:

a constitutive and conservative regime, which reinforces professional identities and protects routines ;

a transformative regime, oriented towards the creation of new organizational narratives, the adaptation of procedures and experimentation.

The challenge, then, is to create a discursive space where these two regimes can coexist, which Cornelissen (2020) describes as organizations' ability to "manage the narrative of their own transformation" to maintain legitimacy while introducing change.

8.2 Communication levers: from information to co-construction

Organizational communication in Senegal's public sector is often thought of in instrumental terms - mainly as the top-down dissemination of information about reforms (Giully, 1992). However, contemporary work in public communication and participative governance (Nabatchi & Leighninger, 2022) shows that sustainable transformation relies on narrative co-construction mechanisms between the various stakeholders: political decision-makers, public agents, social partners and users.

In the public enterprises studied, the absence of structured feedback loops limits the ability to adjust reforms in line with stakeholders' perceptions and needs. COA invites us to consider communication not as a unidirectional flow but as a constitutive practice (Taylor & Van Every, 2014) that shapes the organization itself. For example, the dematerialization of services at La Poste should not just be communicated as a technological project, but narrated as a collective process in which agents redefine their roles and users reformulate their expectations.

8.3 Normative leverage: governing through rules and narratives

The sociology of norms shows that reforms fail when they are limited to modifying texts or organizational charts, without parallel work on normative appropriation. From the perspective of ACOs, this appropriation involves communicative acts that translate formal rules into routines that are meaningful for actors (Koschmann et al., 2012).

The co-construction of norms requires intra-organizational dialogue spaces where agents can discuss, contextualize and negotiate the implementation of reforms. Participatory workshops, when integrated into an internal communication strategy, not only reduce resistance but also strengthen organizational cohesion around a shared narrative of change.

8.4 Socio-cultural leverage: anchoring reform in local contexts

As Diop (1981) points out, Senegalese socio-cultural dynamics shape hierarchical relationships, communication styles and the legitimacy of decisions. By emphasizing the contextualization of communication practices, ACOs encourage the articulation of reforms with local forms of mediation, such as the use of community leaders or social spaces for discussion (daara, local associations, community media).

This hybridization between institutional communication and community communication makes it possible to translate the objectives of administrative modernization into a socially relevant language, thus reducing the divide between the State and its citizens, particularly in rural areas where digital access remains limited (ITU, 2023).

8.5 Towards an integrated communication model for administrative reform

By cross-referencing the lessons learned from ACOs and observations from the case studies, it is possible to propose an integrated model in which :

Strategic storytelling (Cornelissen, 2020) aligns stability and flexibility.

Participatory devices (Nabatchi & Leighninger, 2022) create feedback loops between stakeholders.

Normative translation transforms rules into adapted practices.

Socio-cultural anchoring (Diop, 1981) ensures the relevance and legitimacy of reforms.

In this way, administrative reform becomes a continuous communicative process, in which each interaction contributes to the collective construction of tomorrow's administration.

9. Conclusion

Senegal's administration, through its public enterprises and ministries, is evolving towards a modernity marked by agility and transparency. The crises at SNR, La Poste, Dakar Dem Dikk, SOGEPa and SONACOS, as well as the challenges facing the Ministries of Finance and Civil Service, reveal the importance of organizational communication (Loneux & Bouillon, 2012; Giuily, 1992), normative adaptation (Gaye, 2008), and organizational culture (Schein, 2010). The Senegal 2050 Project offers a promising vision, but its success relies on a hybrid approach, integrating technological innovation, strategic communication and socio-cultural anchoring (Diop, 1981) to improve service to the public.

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